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Guide to NMR Method Development and Validation – Part II: Multivariate data analysis

Authors:

T. Schönberger, Y.B. Monakhova, D.W. Lachenmeier, S. Walch, T. Kuballa, Non-Profit Expert Team (NEXT) -NMR working group Germany

NEXT-NMR-working group Germany in detail:

J. Ammon, C. Andlauer, E. Annweiler, H. Bauer-Aymanns, M. Bunzel, E. Burgmaier-Thielert, T. Brzezina, N. Christoph, H. Dietrich, A. Dohr, O. el-Atma, S. Esslinger, S. Erich, C. Fauhl-Hassek, M. Gary, R. Godelmann, V. Guillou, B. Gutsche, H. Hahn, M. Hahn, A. Harling, S. Hartmann, A. Hermann, M. Hohmann, M. Ilse, H. Koch, H. Köbler, M. Kohl-Himmelseher, K. Klusch, U. Lauber, B. Luy, M. Mahler, S. Maixner, G. Marx, M. Metschies, C. Muhle-Goll, G. Mildau, M. Möllers, C. Neumann, M. Ohmenhäuser, C. Patz, R. Perz, D. Possner, I. Ruge, W. Ruge, R. Schneider, C. Skiera, I. Straub, C. Tschiersch, G. Vollmer, H. Wachter, P. Weller

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Foreword

In the first part of the NMR technical report (see Guide to NMR Method Development and Validation – Part I: Identification and Quantification), the special criteria to facilitate development of NMR-based applications is described. These guidelines (Part I) mostly deal with general requirements, such as NMR spectra acquisition, identification, developing and validation of univariate quantification methods. However, the traditional univariate approach for quantification does not work in case of considerable spectral overlap. Consequently, a range of alternative approaches based on multivariate data treatment (chemometrics) have been appeared and the number of their practical applications for NMR data sets is constantly increasing.

This report provides guidelines for the proper use of chemometrics in NMR analysis, considering NMR spectral pre-processing and discussing some specific requirements separately for multivariate classification and multivariate calibration.

1. General

Chemometrics is the application of mathematical and statistical methods in chemistry. With this formal logic chemical discipline experimental designs can be planned or experimental data can be evaluated [1]. The main idea of chemometric methods based on the so called latent variables or main components is to visualize complex amounts of data and hidden dependences [2]. Kowalski and Reilly were the first who described the analysis of NMR-spectra with chemometrics in 1971 [3]. Along with the fast computer development, chemometric applications increased in the following decades.

There are two groups of chemometric techniques, which are used in analytical spectroscopy in general and are also applicable for NMR spectroscopy. First, methods applied for solving classification problems (i.e., techniques utilized to decide whether a sample is to be classified as belonging to a particular group or – more generally spoken – whether a sample is compliant or non-compliant). This includes, for example, validation of the information provided on the labeling of food and cosmetic products, determination of botanical and geographical origin, or generally authenticity verification (also so-called "non-targeted" NMR). Additionally, multivariate calibration techniques are used for quantification of single

or multiple analytes, when no sufficiently selective NMR signal of the analyte of interest can be identified due to overlap.

1.1 Sample preparation

Standardized sample preparation procedures have to be followed to ensure repeatability and comparability when preparing a series of samples for chemometric analysis. For example, the chemical shifts of some compounds (e.g., organic acids) can be severely affected by the pH in complex matrices (e.g., wine). Therefore, exact pH adjustment (instrumental or manual) is necessary in such cases.

1.2 Acquisition parameters

For the development and validation of an analytical method, where multivariate data analysis is used for spectra modelling, it is important that all spectra are uniformly acquired. It is, therefore, recommended to perform the tuning and to optimize the field homogeneity. It is advisable to check that all the spectra have acceptable line width and line shape. Spectra must be acquired under the same temperature (± 0.1 K). The same pulse program, pulse angle and acquisition parameters (number of scans, acquisition time, spectral width, and receiver gain) have to be used for all spectra intended for multivariate modeling and validation.

1.3 Using of suppression pulse programs

If suppression pulse sequences have to be used to suppress one or multiple resonances (e.g., water and ethanol for alcoholic beverages), it has to be checked that the utilized suppression scheme does not affect signals located closely to the suppressed region (offset-dependent factor $1/F$ is equal for the whole data set) [4].

2 Pre-processing of NMR spectra

2.1 Phase- and baseline correction and referencing

Adequate baseline- and phase correction are fundamental for multivariate spectra modelling. These corrections over the whole spectral range or only for particular regions can be performed automatically or manually. Particular attention should be paid to signals near broad peaks or suppression regions. It is essential to cope with overall sample-to-sample chemical shift variations using general translation of the entire spectrum by an internal reference peak such as 3-(trimethylsilyl)-propionate acid- d_4 (TSP) or tetramethylsilane (TMS).

2.2 Noise reduction

Noise removal before multivariate treatment of the spectra can be done using several routines (e.g., Savitzky-Golay algorithm or using wavelets) [5,6].

2.3 Peak alignment

Chemical shift variations of the same signal of different samples due to random fluctuations are often the case in NMR (so-called misalignment). Methods based on local alignment (such as correlation optimized warping, COW) [7] and icoshift [8]) are relevant for NMR applications. The usage of the icoshift algorithm for biological matrices and food products is described in ref. [9,10]. Alternatively, bucketing can be used to split the entire spectrum into segments (buckets) and the integral of each segment is used as a replacement for the original intensities. The buckets width is a very important parameter for subsequent multivariate analysis, which should vary between 0.01 and 0.05 ppm for ^1H NMR [11]. Some variations of the method are available, including rectangular bucketing, point-wise bucketing, variable size bucketing and advanced bucketing [12]. For practical examples on utilization of bucketing in NMR multivariate method development see ref. [13-16].

2.4 Data reduction

Data reduction facilitates and accelerates chemometric analysis. Elimination of regions with zero intensities as well as regions of solvent and internal reference signals is recommended. Bucketing or taking the average of several data points can be further used for this purpose. In either case all spectra used for multivariate modeling and validation must be processed with the same procedure.

2.5 Variable selection

For selecting the most significant spectral regions for each particular discrimination task, variable selection methods such as clustering of latent variables (CLV) [17] or evolving window zone selection (EWZS) [18] can be used. For multivariate calibration applications one can consider only regions, which contain the resonances of the desired analyte. Advantages of using variable selection techniques in establishing of multivariate model using NMR data are described in ref. [19,20].

2.6 Scaling and centering

Pre-processing can also involve mean-centering and scaling the variables. The mean-centered matrix is obtained by subtracting the mean spectrum (mean intensity for each of the variables) from each spectrum. Second, different types of scaling (scaling to unit variance, Pareto scaling) or, alternatively, element-wise transformations (e.g., log transformations) can be used [21, 22]. Mean-centering is recommended for PCA applications. Fig. 1 shows exemplarily the influence of pre-processing techniques for classification of the geographical origin of wine.

Fig.1. Influence of NMR spectra pre-processing on PCA differentiation of geographical origin of wine: mean-centering (A), auto-scaling (B), and scaling to unit variance (C) (NAH: Nahe, PFL: Pfalz, RHH: Rheinhessen, MSR: Mosel-Saar-Ruwer). The ellipsoids were calculated at 95% probability.

3. General considerations for multivariate analysis of NMR data

3.1 Outlier detection

The detection of outliers and their removal from the calibration set has to be considered prior to building multivariate models. This could be done by using e.g. Mahalanobis distance, non-targeted approach [16] or multivariate control charts [23]. The multivariate model has to be recalculated without the detected outliers. Outliers also have to be excluded from the validation test set.

3.2 Number of significant latent variables

The number of significant latent variables (e.g., principal components in PCA or PLS factors in PLS) has to be determined. The residue of spectral information containing noise has to be excluded from the consideration. Cross validation is the most commonly used technique for this purpose.

3.3 Requirements for samples to be included in calibration sets

The samples used to construct a multivariate model and for its validation have to be authentic and the desired parameter for classification has to be verified (e.g., by a priori knowledge obtained during sampling or by application of an adequate reference method).

If the aim of analysis is to build a multivariate statistical process control (MSPC) model, the best sensitivity is obtained when the samples used for building a model are as close to normal as possible. On the contrary, for classification purposes calibration set should cover the whole population (natural distribution) of samples.

For classification purposes, each predefined group has to contain as much samples as possible (not less than 20 are recommended). The number of samples in a calibration set has not be less than 50 for multivariate calibration. Collinearities of variables caused by correlated

concentrations in calibration samples have to be avoided. Therefore, the composition of calibration mixtures should be chosen according to experimental design [24, 25].

4. Strategies for validation of a multivariate model

It is important to distinguish between the chemometric term “model validation” and the term "method validation", which derives from the field of analytical quality assurance. The first one means that one checks the suitability of a chemometric model and shows its superiority over other alternatives. The second means that one proves the suitability of a complete analytical procedure for the intended purpose. Before the method validation is performed, the validity of the chemometric model has to be proved [26, 27].

4.1 Cross validation

In the cross validation, a few samples are left out from the calibration data set and the model is calibrated using the remaining samples. Then, the values for the left-out samples are predicted and the prediction residuals are computed. Finally, validation residual variance and standard error of cross validation (SECV) are computed. Several versions of the cross validation approach can be used: e.g., full cross validation, segmented cross validation, test-set switch validation and category variable validation.

4.2 Test set validation

Test set validation is the more preferable choice for validation and should be used if there are enough samples in the data table, for instance more than 50. A test set should contain 20-40% of the full data table. The calibration and test sets should cover the whole sample population. Test set must not contain replicate measurements of the same sample.

4.3. Parameters for validation

Parameters that have to be validated for the specific purpose are summarized in the following table:

	Classification	Multivariate calibration
1. Measurement uncertainty		X
2. Precision	X	X

3. Trueness	X	X
4. Limit of detection	X	X ^b
5. Limit of quantification		X ^b
6. Selectivity (Specificity) ^a	X	X
7. Robustness	X	X
8. Working range		X

^a The terms selectivity and specificity have different meanings for classification and multivariate calibration

^b The determination of limit of detection and quantification is not required when the results are in the validated working range

5. Classification

5.1 Classification methods

For classification, unsupervised methods (e.g., PCA), supervised discriminant analysis methods (e.g., linear discriminant analysis (LDA), factorial discriminant analysis (FDA), partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA)) or soft independent modelling of class analogy (SIMCA) can be utilized. Discriminant analysis methods seek for dimensions, which separate predefined groups, and, therefore, are more preferable than PCA.

5.2 Decision criterion (Precision)

A statistically defined decision criterion has to be established, which will be used in routine practice to decide whether a sample is to be classified as compliant or non-compliant.

First, it has to be checked, whether the validation samples or new samples are generally represented by the multivariate model (e.g., by Mahalanobis distance). If this condition is fulfilled, the sample is recognized to belong to a group if it is found inside the prediction ellipsoid in the scores plot within predefined probability (usually 95%). This predefined probability value characterizes the precision of multivariate calibrations.

5.3 Confusion matrix (Trueness)

Confusion matrix is another important tool for method validation, which contains information about the dependence between actual (given, a priori known) and predicted groups done by a

classification tool. As an example, the percentage of correctly classified samples for Riesling wines according to the vintage is shown on Fig.2. The results obtained from a confusion matrix for test sets or cross validation can be considered as a measure of trueness. For further examples see ref. [28-30].

	2005	2006	2007	2009	2010
2005	96	4	0	0	0
2006	0	96	0	2	2
2007	0	0	100	0	0
2009	0	0	0	98	2
2010	0	1	1	6	91

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix for classification of Riesling wines according to the vintage using LDA (diagonal shows the percent of correct classified samples)

5.4 Detection limit

The lowest degree of adulteration that may, with reasonable certainty, be expected to lead to detection of non-compliance has to be determined [31]. Depending on the classification technique used and on the assumptions about the underlying data distribution, different approaches can be employed [31]. Fig. 3 shows a 3D plot, where 25% of falsification of olive oil with sun flower oil can be recognized [31].

Fig.3. Discrimination between ellipsoids of authentic olive oil and olive oil adulterated with sunflower oil [31]

Another example of calculating of detection limit for olive oil adulteration is provided in ref. [32].

5.5. Selectivity and sensitivity

Two other validation parameters of a multivariate model – selectivity and sensitivity – can be calculated for each group from confusion matrix [32]:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \text{true positives} / (\text{true positives} + \text{false negatives})$$

$$\text{Specificity} = (\text{true negatives} / (\text{true negatives} + \text{false negatives}))$$

A practical example of using these parameters for discrimination of rice sorts using NMR can be found in ref. [33].

5.6 Robustness

Effects of variation of experimental parameters (e.g., pH values, high salt concentrations of the sample matrix, reactive chemicals) have to be estimated on the calibration stage. Since the multivariate classification model is constructed it is only suitable for predicting class membership of samples belonging to groups that were predefined during the calibration step. All possible deviations from experimental procedure, acquisition parameters and pre-processing should be avoided.

6. Multivariate calibration

6.1 Multivariate calibration methods

Different multivariate data analysis methods can be applied for multivariate calibration: e.g. multivariate linear regression (MLR), principal component regression (PCR), partial least squares (PLS), latent root regression (LRR), and ridge regression (RR).

6.2 Root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP)

The simplest measure of the uncertainty in multivariate calibration is the RMSEP:

$$RMSEP = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum (Y_{pred} - Y_{ref})^2}$$

Y_{pred} – predicted value by a multivariate model (test set validation)

Y_{ref} – reference value

The results of future predictions can then be presented as $Y_{pred} \pm 2*RMSEP$. This measure is valid when the new samples are similar to the ones used for calibration, otherwise, the prediction error might be much higher.

However, RMSEP has a disadvantage that it is a constant measure for prediction uncertainty that cannot lead to prediction intervals with correct coverage probabilities (for example, 95%). The measurement errors in the response and predictor variables are also neglected in RMSEP. Furthermore, RMSEP underestimates the prediction uncertainty for extreme samples.

The usage of RMSEP to estimate the uncertainty of multivariate models based on NMR spectra is described in [34-36]. For alternative approach (calculating of prediction bands) see section 6.3.

6.3 Measurement uncertainty and prediction bands

In contrast to RMSEP, accurate estimation of the measurement uncertainty in multivariate calibration models should also express how similar the prediction sample is to the calibration samples used to build the model. Predicted Y-values for samples with high deviations cannot be trusted, because they may be outliers.

Basically there are three approaches to correctly estimate measurement uncertainty for each particular sample, prediction bands for the whole multivariate models and the related

performance characteristics that can be derived from them (i.e., trueness, detection limit and quantification limit).

6.3.1 Classical top-down approach

A series consisting of blank samples spiked with increasing amounts of the target analyte, are set, prepared and analyzed. The results obtained using the multivariate calibration model are plotted versus the spiked amounts. Least-squares fitting provides the regression line and the prediction bands, from which the performance characteristics can be inferred similarly to univariate approach, including limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), linear range, and working range. Potential multivariate extensions of generally accepted univariate methodology are listed in [37].

6.3.2 Based on constructed calibration model

The measurement uncertainty and prediction bands can be also computed from the data used to build the multivariate regression model, for example, *Martens-De Vries*, *Kowalski-Faber* and their variations [38-43]. Using these approaches, measurement uncertainty (which is a kind of 95% confidence interval around the predicted Y-value) is computed for each sample as a function of the global model error, the sample's leverage, and its X-residual variance. These expressions intend to generalize the formula that yields the prediction bands for the classical least-squares straight-line fit with intercept. These expressions have an interpretation in terms of multivariate analytical figures of merit. Moreover, they are consistent with expressions for other widely used multivariate quantities, e.g. the scores and loadings from PCA.

The mostly common used equation to estimate uncertainty is the *Kowalski-Faber* formula [40]:

$$yDeviation = \sqrt{ResYValVar \left(\frac{ResXValSamp_{pred}}{ResXValTot} + Hi + \frac{1}{I_{cal}} \right) \left(1 + \frac{A+1}{I_{cal}} \right)}$$

ResYValVar – residual variance per Y-variable for validation samples

ResXValSamp – residual variances per samples in X validation samples

ResXValTot – total residual variance calculated from the residual variances per X-variable for validation samples for A PCs, a = 0 ... A.

Residual variance is defined as the mean squared residual corrected for degrees of freedom.

I_{cal} - total number of observations in the model training set

H_i – leverage of the sample

A – used number of components in the model

6.3.3 Other methods

Prediction bands can be also constructed using bootstrapping or other Monte-Carlo methods [44,45]. These methods are based on much fewer assumptions than the linear regression, being at the same time extremely computationally intensive.

6.4 Precision

To obtain precision values for multivariate models, it is necessary to consider errors that come from the determination of calibration concentrations as well as calibration of instrumental signal (NMR) [37]. Concentration errors are usually available from the details in the preparation of calibration samples, or from the uncertainty in the method employed to determine the reference concentrations. RMSEP on a test set of samples (see section 6.2) can be considered as precision value, which takes into account both error sources [34-37].

6.5 Trueness

The predicted vs. reference plot is an important feature for estimating trueness [24]. The predicted vs. reference plot, constructed for cross validation or test validation, should show a straight line relationship between predicted and measured values, ideally with a slope of 1 and a correlation coefficient of close to 1.

In practice, however, the criteria proposed by Shenk and Westerhaus may be used [46]. According to these authors, an R^2 value greater than 0.90 indicates ‘excellent’ quantitative information, while a value between 0.7 and 0.9 is described as ‘good’. An R^2 value between 0.5 and 0.7 demonstrates good separation of samples into high, medium, and low groups, indicating that the calibration can only be used for screening purposes [46-484].

6.6 Limit of detection (LOD) / Limit of quantification (LOQ)

A rather straightforward approach to estimate the LOD and LOQ values is to apply an error propagation-based formula for standard error of prediction to zero concentration level [37]. This formula takes into account all sources of errors in the data (signals and concentrations) of

calibration and prediction samples and also can be used in cases, when no part in the NMR spectra is selective of the analyte of interest. Other approaches include Monte Carlo simulations based on noise addition, neural classifier, replicate analysis of spiked samples or the analysis of samples with progressively decreasing analyte concentration [37]. All these methods are in mutual agreement with each other [37].

6.7 Selectivity

In contrast to univariate calibration, interference can be adequately modeled using multivariate data. The Lorber-Bergmann-Oepen-Zinn (LBOZ) approach, which accounts for all interference in the mixture, is currently considered as the most suitable one to estimate selectivity [37].

6.8 Working range and robustness

Working range of a multivariate calibration model using NMR starts from the LOQ (lower limit) to the highest analyte concentration in the calibration set.

Multivariate calibration models are only suitable for predicting analytical parameters in matrices that were represented in the calibration set and selected experimental parameters. Any other possible influences of different sources must be examined separately (e.g. pH values, high salt concentrations of the sample matrix, interferences).

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